

*Supporting shared decision-making and communication in breast cancer:
the ShareView project*

Report on developing the self-administered survey
for breast cancer specialists in Europe

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Introduction

One of the primary objectives of the **ShareView** project (Pillar 1) was to design and conduct a **survey** to assess communication practices and the current use of tools and methods that facilitate **shared decision-making (SDM)** in specialist breast units across Europe. This report describes the *development and testing of the survey questionnaire*.

There are two major challenges in measuring SDM behaviour in breast cancer care.

1. The first and most critical challenge is how the concept of SDM is conceptualised and implemented in daily clinical practice, particularly using patient decision aids. Shared decision-making is generally defined as a process of engaging patients in discussing their preferences for different available options and collaborating with clinicians to reach a decision (Zeuner et al. 2015). Despite ongoing research and efforts to promote the adoption of shared decision models into practice, barriers persist in translating this knowledge into routine care, while its real-world impact remains uncertain (Elwyn et al. 2013).

To address this challenge, the questionnaire employs a twofold approach. On one hand, it incorporates an established framework (see below) to examine treatment decision-making around four key models using *paternalistic, informed, deliberative, and shared* anchors (C. A. Charles et al. 2003). On the other hand, the questionnaire provides a clear definition of shared decision-making and patient decision aids as established in the academic literature and clinical guidelines.

2. The second challenge stems from the diversity of healthcare systems, clinical practices, and organisational cultures across Europe. Although clinical practice guidelines exist in many countries (Maes-Carballo et al. 2020), organisational codes and clinicians' styles differ from one country to another, making it difficult to develop a universally applicable questionnaire.

To mitigate this issue, a methodological solution by conducting cognitive testing was adopted. Virtual interviews were conducted with nine clinicians from different European countries to assess the clarity and relevance of a prototype questionnaire. Based on the feedback, three rounds of revisions were implemented.

The survey targets healthcare professionals involved in breast cancer care, including surgeons, medical oncologists, radiologists, and radiation oncologists. While the primary focus is on these specialists, other professionals such as specialised breast nurses and pathologists can also answer the questions. The survey data will be used to:

- Assess clinicians' attitude towards shared decision-making;
- Determine the extent to which SDM-supporting tools are utilised across European breast centres;
- Identify perceived barriers and incentives influencing the implementation of SDM into daily practice.

The following sections detail the development process of the questionnaire, including the review of the literature and available survey instruments around the topic, the methodology for designing survey questions, piloting, and the final revision of the questionnaire. The final

version of the questionnaire, used for distribution, is provided in Annex B. The concluding section outlines the foreseen strategies for survey dissemination.

Design

Survey research is acknowledged as a major technique used in scientific inquiry which follows rigorous design and analysis. The process of developing the survey questionnaire was iterative and followed a systematic approach (Burns et al. 2008). In the next sections are outlined the main steps undertaken to define the questionnaire: (1) item generation and response format; (2) checklist for question design and questionnaire; (3) cognitive testing; and (4) revision and final version.

Step 1: Item generation

To explore the meaning of shared decision-making and self-reported use of tools to promote it, first a scoping literature review was carried out to consider all potential concepts and ideas (items) which could be included in the questionnaire. Based on the results of the review, two relevant streams of research were identified and combined to generate the items of the questionnaire: (i) one underlying the concept of shared decision-making and communication styles; and (ii) the other regarding patient decision aids or other interventions containing DAs, which could foster shared decision-making. Additionally, several existing questionnaires were evaluated as a source of possible questions.

Adopting the framework suggested by Charles and fellows, several questions were generated, using different response formats (C. Charles, Gafni, and Whelan 1997). More specifically, the framework identifies different analytic stages of the treatment decision-making process and proposes four models to reflect *paternalistic*, *informed*, *deliberative* and *shared* approaches to treatment decision-making. The framework constituted the basis for developing and pilot testing a questionnaire via focus groups, subsequently used for collecting survey data among Canadian clinicians (C. A. Charles et al. 2003; C. Charles, Gafni, and Whelan 2004).

Existing questionnaires or guides were revised for content and potential ideas. Namely, a survey tool for identifying barriers and facilitators influencing clinicians to provide support for patients preparing for health decisions, developed in the Ottawa Decision Support Framework¹; several interview guides developed within studies assessing the use of patient decision aid tools (Boateng et al. 2021; Williams et al. 2019).

The first round of revising literature and existing questionnaires contributed to the definition of a list of constructs aimed to be explored. Around these constructs, various questions and statements were built and response formats were developed. The original list contained 16 items, primarily with closed response formats, including binary (yes/no), nominal, ordinal and interval measurements.

Step 2: Guidelines for question design and draft questionnaire

An important aspect of surveys is to ensure that questions are formulated such as to elicit accurate responses. To avoid collecting fallacious responses or omissions, respondents should be able to understand and provide valid answers. This requires a particular attention to the design of questions and their characteristics, including wording, style, punctuation, and length. Moreover, as researchers suggest, the process of questionnaire design should strive for

¹ https://decisionaid.ohri.ca/docs/implement/Pract-DS-Needs_Values.pdf

transparency and replicability while ensuring quality and rigorous review criteria (Beatty et al. 2019).

Towards this end, we have adopted and implemented the framework provided by the Questionnaire Appraisal System (QAS) Manual (Willis and Lessler 1999). QAS was designed to assist users to systematically evaluate survey questions and detect potential problems in wording and structure of the questions that might lead to miscommunication or difficulties in administration, before going into the field. QAS is supplemented with a user manual, which indicates specific review criteria that should be examined for each question in a stepwise fashion and decide whether the question exhibits potentially problematic features.

The assessment process was split into two tracks, one inspected the questionnaire in its entirety following (Schaad, Jans, and Scott 2020); the second used QAS criteria to assess individual questions. More specifically, QAS-99 divides the question review into 8 steps assessing Reading, Instruction, Clarity, Assumptions, Knowledge/memory, Sensitivity/bias, Response categories and Other. The purpose of this first-round assessment was to understand and document any potential issues and reduce them as much as possible. As the authors claim, QAS provides a means to improving the questions and 'flag' questions for further testing (Willis and Lessler 1999).

For the first assessment, we used the original list of generated items and the QAS review criteria to build a matrix to evaluate and revise draft questions (see Figure 1 in Annex). Each question was reviewed against the eight criteria, identifying potential issues of questions overall, response categories, the use of ambiguous words or concepts. The outcome of the assessment contributed to improve the quality of introductions and questions, as well as flagging aspects to be subsequently examined with practitioners.

In the second track we reviewed the questionnaire flow, focusing on the order, logic and relevance of questions, and generally the structure of the questionnaire (see Figure 2 in Annex). As result, the structure of the questionnaire was updated, grouping questions according to the topic and moving question blocks to ease the transition between questions. Furthermore, definitions accredited by health organisations were provided, with embedded links, to avoid concept misinterpretation and disseminate knowledge.

The draft questionnaire that formed the basis of cognitive testing contained 17 questions, but the goal was to filter out and reduce the length of answering time after revisions due to cognitive testing. The draft contained five main sections covering: (i) general presentation of survey goals and informed consent, (ii) profiling questions; (iii) style of communication and patient engagement; (iv) shared decision-making obstacles and enablers; (v) patient decision aids, including use and typologies.

Step 3: Cognitive testing

The need to provide valid, reliable and unbiased research results pushed researchers to adopt methodologies that evaluate survey instruments in a detailed and systematic way, using theories and methods derived from cognitive and social psychology (Collins 2003). Cognitive methods enable researchers to explore the processes by which respondents answer survey questions, and the factors which influence the answer they provide (Idem, 231).

Multiple cognitive methods have been developed and applied to the testing of survey instruments. Cognitive interviewing is one widely employed diagnostic tool for pre-testing

survey instruments. The purpose of cognitive testing is to evaluate whether the respondent interprets the questions in a consistent manner, as intended by the investigator and to judge the appropriateness of each included question.

(Willis 2011) distinguishes two approaches in conducting *cognitive interviews*: 1) the think-aloud technique and 2) verbal probing. To test the questionnaire and facilitate the online interaction process with the respondents, we used a combination of both. Thus, in addition to asking the respondents about how they went about answering, we developed standard probes to explore comprehension, retrieval, judgement and response processes.

To exemplify, for each question potential issues to investigate were listed, then probes were written using the structure below:

- a. How do you decide on the answer?
- b. What, to you, is “_____”
- c. How did you arrive at the response “_____”?
- d. How hard is this for you to answer?

Not all questions were cognitively tested because this would have required interviews to exceed one hour of time. Questions excluded from cognitive interviewing regarded basic, profiling questions of respondents which had been tested previously, such as country, professional role or gender.

Participants involved in the process of cognitive testing were invited following a purposive sampling selection. More specifically, interviewees selected at this stage not necessarily need to be randomly selected but they need to represent some variation in the sample population. The survey was designed to be answered by different health professionals such as surgeons, medical oncologists etc. with different levels of seniority. The goal for interviewee selection was to include different specialists, with each gender adequately covered and varying length of experience. However, specialists having breast cancer as area of practice were excluded. Overall, we were able to interview 9 respondents, including 5 men and 4 women, from 7 different countries spanning from 2 to 40 years of experience. All interviews were recorded and answers systematically loaded in a pre-defined form.

Step 4: Revision and final questionnaire

Out of 17 initially drafted questions 6 were fully revised either by adjusting the question or modifying the response categories (see Table 1 in Annex). After the cognitive interviewing, filtering questions were added to distinguish between users, non-users, and potential users of patient decision aids to collect more accurate responses. Moreover, in the opening section of the survey, clearer instructions for navigation were added, and the informed consent given a higher priority.

The final dataset will include several variables from i) information collected from each respondent for the sampling frame, and ii) from the survey responses. For the first category, variables include country, breast centre certification and volume of activity, professional role and gender of respondents. In the second category, some variables can be used both as a dependent and independent variable, these include both patterns of patient engagement and factors influencing this engagement; as well as use of patient decision aids and determinants of their use.

Dissemination

Before distributing the survey, ethical revision was requested and granted from the Ethical Board of Bocconi University. The approved informed consent was embedded in the opening part of the questionnaire. Because of the difficulty in estimating the exact size of target population, the goal of the survey is to collect data from a nonprobability sampling frame.

The final version of the survey instrument was uploaded on the commercial electronic platform for survey services Qualtrics XM[®]. The platform offers a simple and intuitive layout, allowing easy navigation and completion. If users are unable to complete the questionnaire in one session, they can carry on any time after, provided they use the same computer and internet browser.

Different presentation and dissemination strategies were adopted to distribute it as widely as possible.

First, a presentation letter was written introducing the overall purpose of the project, followed by the description of the self-administered survey. The letter primarily served to introduce the survey and its purpose to different practice and scientific associations in Europe. Both European and national level associations were approached. General associations included European Society of Breast Cancer Specialists (EUSOMA), European Commission Initiatives on Breast and Colorectal Cancer (ECIBS), Breast Surgical Oncology Platform (BRESO), Central-Eastern European Breast Cancer Surgical Consortium (CEEBCSC). Whereas national breast research groups, members of ESMO network, regarded countries like Germany, Finland, Norway, Sweden, Denmark, UK, the Netherlands, Spain. In Italy and France, SenoNetwork and Unicancer represent national networks in different cancer specialists, including for breast disease, which also received the survey for dissemination.

Second, the Breast Centre Network used its professional newsletter to notice members about the launching of the survey. Two subsequent reminders were sent to further engage respondents.

Finally, the survey was presented and brought to public attention during an e-session hosted by the European School of Oncology via e-ESO.net platform. The audience would be redirected to a link of the survey when scanning the provided QR-code.

Due to the open distribution strategy of the survey, the estimation of the actual participation or response rate will be unachievable. The completion rate will be calculated from individuals opening the link.

The survey is expected to be running for a period of five months (April-August 2022) targeting the population of breast cancer specialists.

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Annexes

Figure 1. QAS criteria applied to individual questions

	Encoding: Does the question ask about something that the respondent has noticed and committed to memory?	Reading: Determine if it is difficult for the interviewers to read the question uniformly to all respondents.	Instructions: Look for problems with any introductions, instructions, or explanations from the respondent's point of view.	Clarity: Identify problems related to communicating the intent or meaning of the question to the respondent.	Assumptions: Determine if there are problems with assumptions made or the underlying logic.	Knowledge/Memory: Check whether respondents are likely to not know or have trouble remembering information.	Sensitivity/Bias: Assess questions for sensitive nature or wording, and for bias.	Response Categories: Assess the adequacy of the range of responses to be recorded.	Cross-Cultural Considerations: Assess questions for inappropriate or ineffective cross-cultural references.	Cross-Question: Look for cross-question problems in the entire questionnaire.
Q01. There are no right or wrong answers to the following question. To answer it, please look at the examples given below. Each example shows a different way in which a decision about treatment can be made with a patient. Now think about your approach to decision making with breast cancer patients.		a. no wrong or right answer together with instructions and question - different concepts banded together	a. the instructions are lengthy	a. contains "treatment" which might be ambiguous (treatment after diagnosis or still to establish diagnosis) b. different ways could be confusing when coupled with approaches below	a. we assume a constant behaviour yet radiologists might not be the ones who deliberate with patients	a. "decision making approach" could trigger recalling issues	n/a	a. 5-points likert scale could be tested against 3-points likert scale b. use of underlying to indicate difference b/n approaches	n/a	n/a
Q02. When considering a patient's treatment option, how important are each of the following aspects?		a. information that the aspects are important to the process of deciding a treatment is missing	n/a	a. the frame of reference respondent is supposed to adopt is unclear	n/a	n/a	some response categories might imply socially desirable behaviour	some categories might receive a maximum evaluation in general terms while less evaluation in relative terms		
Q03. Please tell us how much do you agree or disagree with the following statements:									Respondents from different contexts could identify differently the role of nurses and social workers	

Figure 2. Questionnaire flow assessment

Questionnaire flow issues	Error or inefficiency risk	Assessment
Are screener scripts and instructions clear?	If screening and eligibility scripts are not clear, interviewers may interview ineligible households or fail to interview eligible households. This scenario produces coverage errors.	No issues
Is informed consent language provided? Is it clear and easy to read?		Plain language is used but the order could be altered. Clearly state most questions are mandatory , some can be skipped
Is the first question in the questionnaire topic-relevant? If so, are respondents told why less interesting and relevant questions are being asked first?	If the first few questions are difficult, or not topic-relevant, respondents may not continue the interview.	
Are questions with similar timeframes and topics logically grouped together?	Timeframe grouping allows respondents to think about events over a specific timeframe, reducing one source of measurement error. Topic or experience grouping allows respondents to think about all similar topics or experiences together.	Questions are grouped according to the topic. Shared decision-making questions are all ordered in one single section, with a clarifying definition. PtDA are grouped between users and non-users based on filtering questions
How are "don't know" and refusal options dealt with? Are they ever read aloud? Are any questions mandatory?	In general, respondents should be allowed to skip any questions they want to. Core questions, such as those required for within household selection are mandatory, and the interview is discontinued if the respondent will not answer. Rules need to be set for each question	Almost all questions are mandatory except the open-ended question which can be skipped in case the respondent doesn't have anything to fill in
Are there any risks of assimilation, contrast, or priming effects due to question order?	When general questions come first, answers to some survey questions can be influenced by questions asked before them. This risk can be particularly high in multilingual surveys (Lee and Grant, 2009).	To avoid priming effects questions are ordered by asking first attitudes and then specific questions on behaviour
Are respondents only asked questions relevant to them and is skip logic clearly specified?	Limiting questions to only those relevant to respondents by using filter questions makes the entire interview process less burdensome reducing measurement error and hang-ups due to fatigue	Filter questions are used in distinguishing users from non-users and ask relevant questions

Table 1. Final questions after cognitive testing

Block	Question	Action
A	1. There are no right or wrong answers to the following question. To answer it, please look at the examples given below. Each example shows a different approach to how a decision about treatment can be made with a patient with a clear diagnosis. Now think about your approach to decision-making with breast cancer patients. On a scale of 1-5, please indicate your level of comfort in using each of the 4 approaches to treatment decision making described below. (list of 4 examples)	Revised
	2. From your perspective, how important are each of the following to a process of treatment decision making? (list of 6 factors)	Revised
	3. Please tell us how much do you agree or disagree with the following statements (strongly disagree/agree): (list of 8 statements)	Revised
B	1. Is any patient decision aid available in your practice to support treatment decisions?	Not revised
	2. Do you use any patient decision aid to facilitate treatment decisions?	Not revised
	3. Which of the following patient decision aids do you use to facilitate treatment decisions? Tick all that apply.	Amended
	4. If a patient decision aid were available in your organization/country, would you use it in deciding a treatment with your patients?	Not revised
	5. Which of the following best describes the reason(s) for not adopting a patient decision aid? Tick all that apply.	Revised
	6. What aspects do you think are relevant for a patient decision aid? (list of 5 factors)	Revised
C	1. Please select a country in which you currently practice (dropdown menu of countries)	Not revised
	2. Breast Centre certification	Not revised
	3. How many breast cancer patients does your unit treat annually?	Not revised
	4. Please select your current position. (list of 4 categories)	Not revised
	5. What is your seniority? Seniority is defined as the number of years since the end of your residency.	Revised
	6. Please indicate your gender (list of 4 categories)	Not revised